

Comparison of augmentation and pre-processing for deep learning and chemometric classification of infrared spectra

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Abstract

Infrared spectroscopy hampered by physical distortions from scattering and instrumental effects. Therefore, it is generally accepted that spectra should be pre-processed before further data analysis. Deep learning community offers augmentation techniques as an alternative approach to deal with variability in the data. In this paper we propose an Extended Multiplicative Signal Augmentation (EMSA) method for augmenting physical distortions in infrared spectra. In order to study the effect of pre-processing and augmentation techniques we combine them with a wide range of classifiers from chemometrics, machine learning and statistics for four different spectral data sets. While the conventional pre-processing strategies perform well with all classifiers evaluated, augmentation can replace pre-processing when combined with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks and is especially successful when applied to small data sets.

Keywords— chemometrics, pre-processing, augmentation, spectroscopy, classification

1 Introduction

Infrared (IR) spectroscopy studies the interaction between infrared radiation and materials. When mid-IR light penetrates a sample, fundamental vibrations of molecules are excited. Therefore, IR spectra show characteristic signals of different types of chemical bonds and can be used to characterize samples chemically and discriminate chemically different samples. Unfortunately, measured spectra are usually distorted by scattering and instrumental effects. Scattering effects are due to physical conditions of the

samples, while instrumental effects derive from specific measurement conditions. Scattering effects are especially strong in mid-IR microspectroscopy of cells and tissues and make the interpretation of data often impossible unless methods for recovery of pure absorbance spectra are employed [1–3]. Without pre-processing, the subsequent data analysis would be effected by the physical and measurement condition, while the aim of the infrared analysis is to obtain chemical information about the material under investigation. Therefore, it is generally accepted that IR spectra should be pre-processed before further data analysis such as explorative data analysis or model building for classification in order to minimize all non-chemical contributions. Taking derivatives, vector normalization and extended multiplicative signal correction are commonly used pre-processing methods for IR spectra [4, 5]. In other fields, such as in the analysis of images by deep learning, it is common to use data without pre-processing or with very basic standardization procedures such as mean subtraction and feature normalization for model building. Pre-processing has shown to have little or no effect in the domain of image analysis [6, 7]. Today Deep Learning is the state-of-the-art approach in many different areas such as image [8] and audio analysis [9]. It is known as a powerful tool for a data-driven modeling. Usually it requires huge amounts of data. As a point of reference, the database Imagenet [10] contains approximately one million images with annotated bounding boxes of objects. When data sets are not sufficiently large, the deep learning community uses a practice known as *data augmentation*, to satisfy the need for big quantities of data and make model invariant to specific transformations.

Data augmentation is a methodology for data set extension. The main principle is based on applying a range of transformations to the original observations to derive new artificial objects called augmented observations. Augmented observations can then be used for training of classifiers. In order to be successful, data augmentation needs to meet the following requirements: (i) Transformations should change target variables in a known way. In classification problems, transformations are usually supposed to preserve the class of observation; (ii) Transformations should strive to produce observations as close as possible to what could be obtained in reality. For example, in computer vision a horizontal flip of an image satisfies often both conditions, because a flipped object in many cases stays the same. However, there are domains where flipping is not an adequate transformation. For example, in text recognition horizontal flip of text usually is no sense [11]. Data augmentation can be especially beneficial when producing new observations is time-consuming and/or expensive. Augmentation often leads to better and more robust results. One of the last state-of-the-art solutions in computer vision was related to finding correct augmentation policies in data [12]. While it is intuitive and straight forward to devise augmentation for general images such as cats and dogs, where flipping, translations and rotations are common approaches, augmentation for IR spectral data needs to start with *a priori* knowledge about variations in IR spectra due to different physical and measurement conditions.

Very few studies have been performed on augmentation and deep learning in the field of infrared spectroscopy. The earliest study performed by Conlin et al. [13] attempted to augment an IR data set by Gaussian noise with subsequent analysis by Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR). One of the recent studies showed that Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) are performing better than PLSR both with and without pre-processing, while augmentation was not found to be beneficial [14]. Another recent study found that augmentation of near-infrared spectra by adding baseline, slope and multiplicative variations is useful [15]. However, the differences in model performance between augmented and pre-processed data were marginal for the near-infrared data investigated. Lately, a neural network based on Inception architec-

ture [16] was proposed and it was stated that there is no need in pre-processing of IR spectral data, while augmentation was not evaluated in this study [17].

In our paper we propose an augmentation method for IR spectral data, which can be seen as a generalization of the method proposed by Bjerrum et al. [15]. We build augmentation in the framework of Extended Multiplicative Signal Correction (EMSC) [18], a method commonly applied by the infrared spectroscopy community. The open-source implementation is available at <https://github.com/BioSpecNorway/EMSA>. To investigate the performance of the proposed method in infrared spectroscopy, we evaluate different augmentation and pre-processing techniques in combination with a wide range of multivariate and machine learning classifiers for two mid-infrared and two near-infrared data sets.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Data sets

Different combinations of pre-processing, augmentation and classifiers were evaluated for four data sets. Two of them were Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectral data sets of yeasts [19] and moulds [20]. The other two data sets are publicly available Near Infrared (NIR) spectra of pharmaceutical tablets [21] (<http://eigenvector.com/data/tablets/>) and NIR spectra of corns (www.eigenvector.com/Data/Corn/). The tablet data set has been previously used in corresponding research studies on pre-processing and augmentation [14, 15, 17]. The corn data set was only used in the work of [17]. It was interesting to consider it for comparison, since it contained a very small number of spectra.

2.1.1 FTIR data sets

The yeast FTIR data set consists of in total 1943 spectra of 93 different yeast strains of 13 genera [19]. The yeast strains were cultivated in five growth media in six biological replicates. The six biological replicates are independent cultivation runs and experiments, performed at different time points. This means that six independent sub-sets of IR spectra were available for each cultivation medium. For the current paper we used the six independent cultivation experiments for yeasts cultivated in the growth medium Sabouraud broth (SAB).

The mould data set consists of in total 1029 spectra of fifty nine moulds strains of 10 genera. The fungal strains were cultivated on malt extract broth (MEB) growth medium in six biological replicates. The six biological replicates were obtained from independent experiments in the same way as the yeast data set [20].

Infrared spectra of yeasts and moulds were recorded in the region between 4000 and 500 cm^{-1} with a spectral resolution of 6 cm^{-1} (3629 and 3627 channels, respectively). A detailed description of the yeast and mould experiments and the acquisition of IR spectra can be found in the references [19, 20], respectively.

The number of strains per genus for both data sets is shown in Table 1. Both data sets were imbalanced, since each genus contained different numbers of species and strains. For the yeast data set, each independent cultivation run includes about 320 spectra. For the moulds data set, all runs except run 3, had about 190 spectra, while run 3 had only 76 spectra.

The target for the classification in this study is to classify according to the genus level.

Table 1: Overall number of spectra per genus in yeast and mould data sets

Yeasts		Moulds	
Genus	Count	Genus	Count
<i>Candida</i>	279	<i>Alternaria</i>	64
<i>Clavispora</i>	33	<i>Aspergillus</i>	240
<i>Debaryomyces</i>	73	<i>Eurotium</i>	124
<i>Hanseniaspora</i>	86	<i>Fusarium</i>	160
<i>Issatchenkia</i>	41	<i>Geotrichum</i>	32
<i>Lodderomyces</i>	24	<i>Mucor</i>	84
<i>Metchnikowia</i>	57	<i>Paecilomyces</i>	16
<i>Pichia</i>	403	<i>Penicillium</i>	208
<i>Rhodotorula</i>	88	<i>Phoma</i>	24
<i>Saccharomyces</i>	491	<i>Rhizopus</i>	77
<i>Torulaspota</i>	204		
<i>Trichosporon</i>	24		
<i>Zygosaccharomyces</i>	135		
Total	1943	Total	1029

2.1.2 NIR data sets

The tablet data set is a popular data set used for bench marking data analysis methods [14, 15, 17, 22] and consists of 655 NIR spectra of pharmaceutical tablets, measured in a region from 600 to 1898 nm with a resolution of 2 nm (650 channels) [21]. Spectra were randomly and evenly split into six folds (about 110 spectra per fold).

The corn data set contained 80 sample spectra of corn, which were measured on three different spectrometers. In this study we used a data set of 80 NIR spectra acquired by a MP6 spectrometer. The spectra had a range from 1100 to 2498 nm with the spectral resolution of 2 nm (700 channels) (www.eigenvector.com/Data/Corn/). Spectra were randomly and evenly split into 4 folds (20 spectra per fold).

The tablet and corn data sets have continuous target variables. In order to establish a classification problem we clustered them by KMeans into seven and three classes, respectively.

2.2 Pre-processing

2.2.1 Extended Multiplicative Signal Correction

The aim of the EMSC pre-processing is to correct spectra for various physical and instrumental distortions [1], such as variations in the light source between measurement of background and sample (baseline shift) variations in thickness of samples (multiplicative effect), instrumental effects and scattering (spectrum sloping). The basic EMSC model of a measured spectrum can be written as follows

$$\bar{A}(\tilde{\nu}) = a + m(\tilde{\nu}) \cdot b + d_1 \tilde{\nu} + d_2 \tilde{\nu}^2 + \dots + d_n \tilde{\nu}^n \quad (1)$$

$$A(\tilde{\nu}) = \bar{A}(\tilde{\nu}) + e(\tilde{\nu}) \quad (2)$$

where $A(\tilde{\nu})$ is a measured absorbance spectrum, $m(\tilde{\nu})$ is the reference spectrum, a, b, d_1, \dots, d_n are the parameters related to the baseline, multiplicative, linear and higher polynomial terms, respectively. The term $e(\tilde{\nu})$ takes into account the unmodelled residual of the measured spectrum. As reference spectrum we can either choose a representative spectrum, preferably without scatter distortions, or we can just calculate it as the average of the sample set. The EMSC model accounts for the average chemical absorption properties. In a given set of spectra the interesting chemical variations around the average absorbance spectrum are usually small. They are included in the error term $e(\tilde{\nu}) = A(\tilde{\nu}) - \bar{A}(\tilde{\nu})$ which is ideally free from physical distortions and contains only the chemical variations of each spectrum with respect to the reference spectrum.

The equation 1 can be written as a system of equations, because $\tilde{\nu}$ is a finite set of wavenumbers for which the absorbance $A(\tilde{\nu})$ was measured. The set of equations can be represented in matrix form

$$\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{p} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}$$

where \mathbf{a} is a column-vector representing the raw spectrum, which is to be corrected, \mathbf{M} is a matrix, which consists of columns representing the reference spectrum, a column of ones, a column of $\tilde{\nu}$, a column of $\tilde{\nu}^2$ etc, \mathbf{p} is a column-vector of unknown parameters, and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ is a column vector representing the error.

We can solve this equations for the vector \mathbf{p} with the help of the least squares method. The solution can be written as follows:

$$\mathbf{p} = (\mathbf{M}^T \mathbf{M})^{-1} \mathbf{M}^T \cdot \mathbf{a} \quad (3)$$

When the column vector of parameters is estimated by least squares, we can estimate the corrected spectrum as follows:

$$A_{corr}(\tilde{\nu}) = \frac{A(\tilde{\nu}) - a - d_1 \tilde{\nu} - d_2 \tilde{\nu}^2 - \dots - d_n \tilde{\nu}^n}{b} = m(\tilde{\nu}) + \frac{e}{b} \quad (4)$$

Usually, in infrared spectroscopy we use parameters up to the quadratic term d_2 in order to avoid that polynomial terms of higher order fit chemical absorption bands in the spectrum. More detailed explanation of the EMSC method in infrared spectroscopy can be found in [1].

In fact, the EMSC framework is not restricted to model physical effects in measured spectra with polynomials in addition to the reference spectrum. In general, EMSC can be considered as a framework that can account for different types of variation in a spectrum. For example, it is possible to add interferent spectra such as a spectrum of water in the EMSC model and thus remove water variation in samples [2]. It is further possible to model complex scatter phenomena such as Mie scattering by implementing the van de Hulst approximation of Mie scattering and thus account for the Mie scattering [3].

2.2.2 Derivatives based pre-processing

Another well-known technique for pre-processing spectra is taking derivatives w.r.t. wavenumbers. It is obvious that taking the first derivative removes all constant contributions to a spectrum. In other words the first derivative removes constant baseline shifts in a spectrum. Accordingly, the second derivative additionally removes linear contributions of a spectrum in addition to the constant baseline. It has been shown that it is beneficial to take derivatives before EMSC correction, because the parameter estimate in EMSC is more precise if it is done in this order [5]. The second derivative is a frequently used approach for spectral band deconvolution. In infrared spectroscopy, it is usually performed by the Savitzky-Golay algorithm which allows to locally smooth a spectrum by using a window of a certain size and to subsequently take the derivative.

2.3 Extended Multiplicative Signal Augmentation (EMSA)

In this section, we introduce Extended Multiplicative Signal Augmentation as an approach to augment infrared spectral data sets by physical variation. The idea is to first estimate physical parameters related to scattering and instrumental effects by EMSC (see 2.2.1) and then augment a given data set by introducing similar physical effects and thereby generating new data. In order to augment a given data set with relevant physical parameters, we estimate the range of each EMSC parameter from a measured data set and generate new parameter values by adding a random deviation to the old parameters.

Thus, in order to create new artificial spectra by augmentation, we first calculate the parameters a, b, d_1, d_2, \dots (physical parameters) by EMSC for each spectrum in the training set. Then we calculate the standard deviation for each parameter ($\sigma_a, \sigma_b, \dots$). To obtain an augmented spectrum from a measured spectrum, we draw a set of deviations ($\Delta a, \Delta b, \dots$) from normal distributions using zero mean and the respective standard deviations for each parameter. Finally, we add the drawn deviations to the parameters of each measured spectrum (e.g. $a' = a + \Delta a$). Generation of new parameters around the old ones helps to preserve correlation between them and thus helps to avoid generation of unnatural independent parameters.

Thus a new augmented spectrum can be obtained as:

$$A_{new}(\tilde{\nu}) = a' + m(\tilde{\nu}) \cdot b' + d'_1 \tilde{\nu} + d'_2 \tilde{\nu}^2 + \dots + d'_n \tilde{\nu}^n + \frac{e(\tilde{\nu}) \cdot b'}{b} \quad (5)$$

where $a', b', d'_1, d'_2, \dots$ are the new simulated parameters.

Bjerrum et al. [15] proposed augmentation of spectral data by varying baseline, slope and multiplicative effects. EMSA goes further and suggests that it is possible to augment all variability accounted by the EMSC-model which is a more general approach. Augmentation can therefore also be applied to chemical variation, variation accounted for by ME-EMSC model [3] and fringes-EMSC [23]. Thus, augmentation proposed in [15] is a special case of EMSA where only a first order polynomial is used (i.e. it augments a, b and d_1 parameters). EMSC is a model-based method that allows incorporating physical models for scattering and instrumental variability. EMSA takes this advantage of EMSC.

The open-source implementation in python can be found at <https://github.com/BioSpecNorway/EMSA>.

2.4 Pre-training routines

In order to not confuse pre-processing and augmentation, we do not term augmentation by pre-processing in this paper. We term all data manipulations that take place before training a classifier (i.e. pre-processing and augmentation) by pre-training routines.

For pre-processing we used second derivative by Savitzky-Golay with a second order polynomial and 19 smoothing points (SG (2, 19)), EMSC with a second order polynomial (EMSC (2)) and their combination (SG (2, 19) + EMSC (2)).

For augmentation we used the proposed EMSA method with a first and second order polynomial (the order is stated in parenthesis). EMSA with a first order polynomial is identical to the augmentation proposed by Bjerrum et al..

EMSA augmentation was run in two different modes. The first mode of augmentation is creating a new data set with an established number of augmented spectra per class (e.g. routine Aug(1000, 2) added to training set 1000 artificial spectra per class). The second mode is a batch augmentation, which is only applicable to neural networks (Batch Aug (1) and Batch Aug (2)). Neural networks are usually trained by a technique called mini-batch gradient descent. It means that the training set is split into batches, for example each containing 32 spectra. Then the mean gradient is computed across the batch and the weights of the neural network are updated. Batch augmentation means that each batch gets *transformed* during gradient descent search. Since spectra are continuously changed during the gradient descent search, the data set, that is generated simultaneously during weights optimization, becomes very large. Thus, batch augmentation consists of a transformation of batches of original spectra to feed the neural network until it stops to improve results. In this mode only artificial spectra are fed, but a new generated spectrum can be quite close to the original if all perturbations to parameters are sampled close to zero. The data set produced during the second mode is very large and can be considered as an infinitely large data set.

Finally, we considered a combination of EMSA augmentation and pre-processing with a second derivative by Savitzky-Golay (Aug (1000, 2) + SG (2, 19)). We did not add EMSC after augmentation, since EMSC is expected to cancel out the effect of augmentation (see Sec. 3.1.2).

2.5 Classifiers

To investigate the effect of the proposed augmentation we have employed a wide range of chemometrics and machine learning classifiers. Among those are K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Partial Least Squares (PLS-DA), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). We employed two architectures of CNN: DeepSpectra proposed by [17] and one developed by us (section 2.6).

We used nested n-fold cross-validation for hyperparameter optimization and for testing of the performance of the established models. The folds that were defined in sec. 2.1 refer to independent data and are therefore well suited as "test" sets. As an example, the folds defined for the FTIR data, refer to independent experiments run at different days. The outer loop of the cross-validation was used to test the models' performance and the inner loop was used to optimize hyperparameters of KNN, PLS-DA, SVM and RF classifiers. For the neural networks, we used one of the inner folds for deciding when to stop the training process.

For hyperparameter optimization a grid search algorithm was used. SVM was used

with a linear kernel and the penalty term C was searched across four values 0.01, 0.1, 1 and 10. RF was employed with 100 trees, no maximal depth and a minimum of two samples for splitting an internal node. A maximal number of features was searched across five evenly spaced values in the interval from 10 to square root of the number of channels in the spectra. The number of components for the PLS-DA classifier was searched in the range from 1 to 40. For the KNN classifier, Pearson’s correlation was used as a distance metric and the number of neighbors was searched across 1, 3 and 5.

Scikit-learn implementations [24] of KNN, SVM and RF were used. A PLS-DA classifier was implemented based on the scikit-learn implementation of PLSRegression. The Keras framework [25] was used for training convolutional neural networks. For DeepSpectra we took the suggested hyperparameters for the wheat dataset from the original paper [17].

2.6 VGG-like architecture of neural network

We also wanted to investigate if a simple CNN with four times less weights than DeepSpectra can provide comparable results. We derived a CNN from the well-known VGG architecture [26]. The VGG architecture consists of similar blocks of layers (vgg-block for shortness). Each vgg-block contains two convolutional layers followed by a pooling layer. The VGG architecture is built on two main ideas. The first idea is that after each vgg-block the spatial resolution decreases twice, but the number of features doubles in order to make sure that the next vgg-block has twice more convolutional filters than the previous one and pooling size equals to two. Another idea is that two stacked convolution layers with kernel size 3x3 result in a receptive field 5x5, but at the same time have less weights than one convolutional layer of size 5x5.

The proposed neural network consists of four vgg-blocks followed by a Dropout layer (with rate 0.5) and a fully-connected layer for classification. The filter size is three and the first vgg-block has 12 filters, the next vgg-blocks have 24, 48 and 96 filters. The only difference is that first vgg-block has pooling size 8 and stride 4, i.e. it reduces spatial resolution four times. We further added a Batch Normalization layer after each convolutional layer and used AveragePooling instead of MaxPooling.

This simple architecture resulted in 170 thousands weights for a single spectrum with 3500 channels, which is a lower number of weights compared to the 750 thousands weights in the DeepSpectra [17] and 26 millions weights in the CNN used by Bjerrum et al. [15]. We will denote our proposed CNN as SpectraVGG. The proposed SpectraVGG is openly accessible (<https://github.com/BioSpecNorway/EMSA>).

3 Results and Discussion

Both NIR data sets are provided with continuous response variables and pose a regression problem. Therefore, we established a classification problem by defining classes using KMeans clustering. Target variables of tablets data set (weight, hardness and assay) and corns data set (starch, protein, oil) were clustered into seven and three classes, respectively (Fig. 1). The obtained classes were used for establishing classifiers.

Figure 1: *Defining classes for corn and tablet data sets: KMeans clustering was used to establish seven and three classes.*

3.1 Comparison of pre-processing and augmentation

In order to compare augmentation visually with pre-processing strategies, we grouped pre-training routines by type of applied methods, i.e. raw (no pre-processing) pre-processing, augmentation and combined use of pre-processing in Fig. 2. While Fig. 2 presents the classification results visually, the corresponding numeric results are given in detail in Table 2. The pre-processing method using second derivative by Savitzky-Golay followed by EMSC has shown to be one of the most powerful pre-processing strategies for FTIR data [5]. In the current study, we use it therefore as the **benchmark pre-processing technique**. Savitzky-Golay requires to chose a set of parameters. We have in a previous study evaluated approaches for optimizing the parameters Savitzky-Golay [5]. We found that parameter settings involving 19 smoothing points combined with Extended multiplicative signal correction, a second order polynomial both for second derivative by Savitzky-Golay and EMSC gave overall the best results for the data sets considered. The Savitzky-Golay parameters may be further optimized for each single data set. However, we preferred to used the best compromise for a comparison of results obtained for several data sets. We see clearly that second derivative by Savtizky-Golay followed by EMSC performs well for all classifiers and data sets. This is in accordance with previous studies [5].

3.1.1 The deep learning classifiers perform well for all pre-training routines

Figure 2 summarizes graphically the results of combinations of all pre-training routines and classifiers. The results for the different data sets are summarized in four different graphs. For each data set, the first bar shows the results for raw data in red, and the second bar shows the benchmark results (SG + EMSC) in purple. For all other bars, the bars indicate the best results within one group: orange bars give the best results within all pre-processing options used, green bars give the best results within all augmentation procedures used and blue bars give the best results within all combined routines used. Black dashes indicate individual results for the pre-training routines.

From Figure 2 we can see that the deep learning approach have throughout a high performance for all used pre-training routines (except for the corn data set). While overall the neural networks perform best, very good results can be achieved with conventional classifiers as well. For tablet data, SVM perform better than all other methods. RF works very well for the yeast, mould and tablet data. For raw data,

Figure 2: Results for each pre-training routine in comparison with Raw (red) and benchmark routine (SG (2, 19) + EMSC(2)) (purple). Pre-training routines grouped by type: only pre-processing (orange), only augmentation (green), combined (blue). Individual results of pre-training routines are indicated by black dashes within each bar to visualize the spread of the results within each group.

Table 2: Mean accuracy of classifiers combined with pre-training routines for four data sets. SG – Savitzky-Golay, Aug – Augmentation (EMSA) with added original data. Parameters description can be found in Sec. 2.4

Pre-training routine	KNN	PLS	SVM	RF	DS	SVGG
Yeasts (HTS-FTIR, 2000 samples)						
Raw	73.2	88.7	88.7	58.4	91.5	88.3
SG (2, 19)	81.9	88.3	88.5	93.1	91.5	93.2
EMSC (2)	83.8	90.3	91.7	87.5	92.5	90.8
SG (2, 19) ▶ EMSC (2)	88.5	89.9	90.8	94.4	93.7	94.3
Aug (1000, 2)	73.6	88.1	88.5	73.3	90.5	93.3
Batch Aug (1)	-	-	-	-	91.6	92.8
Batch Aug (2)	-	-	-	-	91.5	93.0
Aug (1000, 2) ▶ SG (2, 19)	82.0	87.1	84.8	94.7	91.3	92.7
Moulds (HTS-FTIR, 1000 samples)						
Raw	79.2	90.6	84.2	63.0	91.4	89.8
SG (2, 19)	82.2	89.4	91.4	94.7	93.3	93.7
EMSC (2)	84.9	93.0	87.0	86.7	93.0	91.4
SG (2, 19) ▶ EMSC (2)	90.1	89.0	93.6	94.9	92.8	95.7
Aug (1000, 2)	82.2	90.0	81.9	76.1	92.4	94.5
Batch Aug (1)	-	-	-	-	93.7	94.4
Batch Aug (2)	-	-	-	-	93.9	93.3
Aug (1000, 2) ▶ SG (2, 19)	85.2	87.8	83.2	94.7	90.8	95.2
Tablets (NIR, 655 samples)						
Raw	64.9	73.8	91.0	82.0	80.2	88.4
SG (2, 19)	77.4	74.8	92.4	91.8	88.3	90.1
EMSC (2)	78.3	75.8	92.7	89.3	82.7	88.7
SG (2, 19) ▶ EMSC (2)	73.0	74.3	92.5	90.8	88.7	89.6
Aug (1000, 2)	63.2	68.4	87.5	88.9	79.7	88.5
Batch Aug (1)	-	-	-	-	81.2	88.6
Batch Aug (2)	-	-	-	-	81.5	89.5
Aug (1000, 2) ▶ SG (2, 19)	76.6	68.8	85.1	91.0	89.3	89.5
Corns (NIR, 80 samples)						
Raw	51.2	74.8	76.2	33.7	68.4	55.7
SG (2, 19)	74.5	61.2	73.7	63.6	63.7	67.4
EMSC (2)	72.3	54.7	66.3	67.5	63.9	73.7
SG (2, 19) ▶ EMSC (2)	74.8	59.8	68.8	70.2	65.3	68.7
Aug (1000, 2)	61.2	56.0	78.7	42.1	77.3	75.0
Batch Aug (1)	-	-	-	-	81.0	80.0
Batch Aug (2)	-	-	-	-	80.1	77.5
Aug (1000, 2) ▶ SG (2, 19)	74.6	57.7	76.4	69.0	71.3	81.2

the neural networks work generally better. It is expected that deep learning classifiers achieve a high accuracy when trained on raw data, since deep learning classifiers are

capable of learning complex pre-processing as part of the classifier establishment [27]. Acquarelli et al. [14] reported that neural networks were able to learn which are the chemically important regions, even when trained on raw data. These results are in agreement with other papers [14, 15, 17]. However, even though they achieve a high accuracy when using raw data, the classification results are better if they are combined with pre-processing or augmentation. This is notable since Zhang et al. [17] reported that for a (quantitative) regression task, DeepSpectra worked better without pre-processing.

3.1.2 Simple classifiers depend on pre-processing and augmentation

Our results show further that in contrast to deep learning, simple classifiers such as KNN, PLS, SVM and RF, depend strongly on the pre-processing and the augmentation strategy chosen (see Fig. 2). The performance of the classifiers when applied to FTIR data improves considerably, when they are used in combination with the benchmark pre-processing (SG + EMSC). This routine is depicted by the purple column in Figure 2. It can be seen that the results obtained with this pre-processing routine are among the best results for each classifier except for the corn data set. Our results show that simple classifiers do not benefit from just augmentation. The reason is that in contrast to neural networks, simple classifiers do not have a high flexibility to learn to suppress complex variability and therefore usually need to use more handcrafted features. Pre-processing helps to identify and select the relevant features and leads to suitable representation that allows simple classifiers to perform well. As opposed to pre-processing, data augmentation helps to identify variability in the data and helps the model to learn it.

In cases where little or no knowledge is available *a priori*, e.g. about the physical variability in the data set, pre-processing models may be difficult to establish and data augmentation would be the better choice. However, when unwanted variability can be modelled by model-based pre-processing, it is often an advantage to separate physical effects. In addition, model-based pre-processing allows to analyse physical effects separated from the pure chemical features in spectroscopy. This may improve the insight in the physical and chemical nature of classification results [1, 28]: in infrared microspectroscopy, physical effects are often due to informative scattering signatures, which carry information about cell morphology and shapes of cell components [29]. Physical effects may hide relevant information for classification. This variation can either be separated by model-based pre-processing and investigated separately or it can be handled without separating and modelling it separately by neural networks when the data sets are large enough. Therefore, it may not always be necessary or beneficial to remove scattering from the IR spectral data.

3.1.3 Augmentation improves classifiers trained on small data sets considerably

We observe that the classification results for the corn data set were improved considerably when using augmentation with neural networks (Fig. 2 (d)). For larger data sets the gain is small compared to the benchmark pre-processing (SG + EMSC).

Although pure augmentation combined with simple classifiers gives inferior results as can be seen from Fig. 2 (d), simple classifiers may benefit from augmentation in the cases where augmentation is combined with pre-processing. Here augmentation clearly works as a regularization, i.e. it reduces the variance of model. By introducing

new artificial spectra, augmentation makes it possible for a flexible classifier to learn how to treat distortions due to physical effects resulting in more precise classification on boundaries.

However, it is important to notice that if extended multiplicative signal augmentation (EMSA) is followed by EMSC where the same parameters are used in the EMSC correction as in the EMSA, the EMSC is expected to neutralize the effect of the augmentation completely. This effect is expected since in the basic EMSC model, the model spectra are pretty independent of each other and EMSC is therefore able to estimate the parameters that were used for augmentation to a high precision and to remove them. We compared pre-processing regimes where EMSA was followed by EMSC (e.g. EMSA \blacktriangleright SG \blacktriangleright EMSC) with situations where EMSC but not EMSA was used in the pre-processing (SG \blacktriangleright EMSC) and obtained in all situations comparable results (results not shown). This implies that EMSA was almost entirely neutralized when followed by EMSC pre-processing and effectively we made an oversampling by duplicates. The obtained results are in contrast to the results presented in Bjerrum et al. [15]. Bjerrum et al. [15] reports that EMSC applied after augmentation with EMSC parameters, i.e. baseline, multiplication and slope variations, resulted in a better performance of the classifier compared to when just augmentation was used, and concluded that the improved results were due to residual variations left after EMSC correction. Our hypothesis is that not the combination of EMSA and EMSC, but rather EMSC itself performed better than augmentation for the specific case presented by Bjerrum et al. [15]. When EMSC is used after augmentation it neutralizes the effect of augmentation and corrects in addition all spectra with respect to multiplicative and baseline effects. We further want to point out that it is important to use relevant transformations for the augmentation. For example, when we added two naive transformations to EMSA: Gaussian noise and horizontal shift to the whole spectrum, we observed that this choice eventually resulted in a slightly negative effect on the classification results. The reason for this is that the data is obviously not effected by a substantial level of Gaussian noise or by horizontal shifts. Horizontal shifts are not expected for example in FTIR spectroscopy, while they are common in Raman spectroscopy [30].

3.1.4 Bigger size of augmentation leads to better results

In Figure 2, we can see that within each *augmentation* group (green bar) there is a quite spread indicating that the size of augmentation matters. Figure 3 shows how classification results depend on the size of the augmentation for all four data sets in (a)-(d), respectively. The solid lines show results of *augmentation* routines, where the original training set was used together with augmented spectra. The first data point of each graph relates to the use of only raw data and can be considered as a reference for comparison. It can be clearly seen that accuracy tends to increase for the neural networks and random forest when the augmentation size is increased. We can see that augmentation does not really have a strong effect on the data sets that are comparably large (yeasts, moulds and tablets) compared to using only raw data. The biggest effect of the augmentation is observed for the small data set of corn. Further, we notice that even though batch augmentation used only augmented (artificial) spectra, it has a high accuracy which was not inferior to the accuracy obtained with augmentations of fixed sizes including additionally original spectra. This is expected, since EMSA can produce a very similar spectrum to original one when spectra with very small disturbances are generated (see Sec. 2.3). The number of spectra with small disturbances is high in

batch augmentation, since it effectively generates a very large data set. However, for a fixed size augmentation we always got better results when original spectra were included.

Figure 3: Change of accuracy depending on augmentation size. DS – DeepSpectra, SVGG – SpectraVGG.

We plotted wavenumbers importance for random forest classifier in Fig. 4. We observed that accuracy increased with an increase of augmentation size for the RF classifier, which indicates that RF can learn better features with the proposed augmentation method compared to using only raw data. We observed that important regions become more well defined and noise regions received lower scores with increasing augmentation size. In addition, with pre-processing by second derivative, random forest learned more distinct features in chemical active regions. In both cases, augmentation made the CO_2 region from 2200 to 2400 cm^{-1} and noise region around 4000 cm^{-1} less important for random forest. A more detailed study of feature importance for PLS and RF classifiers for the yeast data set can be found in [31].

3.1.5 Class-wise augmentation

We conducted several simulations where EMSA used ranges for augmentation which were specific for each class of spectra that was augmented (e.g. according to the genus). In all cases, class-wise augmentation showed results that were slightly worse than results that were obtained when the choice of range used for augmentation was based on the whole training set. This implies that the relevant physical variations are

Figure 4: Importance of wavenumbers for the random forest classifier trained on the yeast data set. The thick line refers to a sample spectrum of yeast and the thin line indicates the importance of the wavenumbers

not specific to a biological class. However, we may imagine cases, where class-wise augmentation could improve the models. E.g. in infrared microscopy, when different species exhibit different morphologies as it is the case for pollen grains [29]. Here class-wise augmentation may be beneficial.

3.1.6 Comparison with augmentation proposed by Bjerrum et al. [15]

As it was stated in sec. 2.3, the augmentation proposed by Bjerrum et al. [15] is a special case of EMSA, when EMSA utilizes a first order polynomial and does not have additional constituents. Therefore, Batch Augmentation using a first order polynomial, is considered to be very close to augmentation proposed by Bjerrum et al. From results in Table 2 we can see that for some of the cases it is beneficial to add a quadratic effect as well. E.g. for the mould data set, a higher accuracy is obtained when quadratic effects are simulated, while for the corn data set it is not beneficial. In general we can state that the generalization to EMSA is expected to be beneficial in many situations where interferences have been modelled by EMSC such as fluorescence in Raman spectroscopy, water vapor, carbon dioxide, water and Mie scattering [2, 3, 32, 33]. This shows that the idea of generalization by EMSC is valuable, because it allows to adapt augmentation to different physical effects that can be observed in spectroscopic data.

3.2 Efficiency of CNNs for the spectral data

Recently, several architectures for neural networks were proposed [14,15,17,34]. Figure 2 clearly shows that both convolutional neural networks show a high performance for all pre-training routines and data sets. Although SpectraVGG has four times less parameters than DeepSpectra, it produces comparable results to DeepSpectra. Moreover, SpectraVGG appears to be more stable across different routines than DeepSpectra. Figure 2 shows that DeepSpectra works better, when pre-processing or augmentation is applied to raw data. This is in contrast to [17], who reported that pre-processing does not improve DeepSpectra performance for spectral data.

It is interesting to note that in such a setup, the activation function LeakyReLU gave a significant gain in comparison with ReLU for SpectraVGG. We also experienced that DeepSpectra converged much faster when 2nd derivative by Savitzky Golay was applied.

4 Conclusions

Data augmentation is an artificial extension of variability in a data set to give the classifier more data to learn this variability, while pre-processing prior to building a classifier tries to remove this variability. The augmentation method proposed in this paper introduces typical physical distortions observed in spectra in order to allow powerful models such as CNNs to build more accurate borders between the classes due to an augmented information on physical distortions in spectra. Therefore, we expect that CNNs learn a better way of accounting for such distortions.

The here presented Extended Multiplicative Signal Augmentation (EMSA) is based on the well-known EMSC technique allowing augmentation of physical effects in spectra. The EMSA method can replace pre-processing for convolutional neural networks, but for conventional classifiers, a mixture of pre-processing and augmentation can help to improve results when data sets are small. EMSA augmentation is especially beneficial for small data sets. We achieved a 10% improvement in accuracy on a data set that contains only 80 samples. Nevertheless, it is important to note that physical augmentation cannot introduce chemical information and therefore it cannot replace measurement of new samples that could increase the chemical variability. In other words, results improved not because we achieved an enhanced learning of differences between classes, but because the classifier learned how to better account for physical distortions.

In contrast to [17], we showed that convolutional neural networks applied to spectral data benefit from traditional pre-processing as well. For CNNs, the results are better and the convergence is much faster when they are combined with traditional pre-processing.

The CNN proposed in this work (SpectraVGG) is based on VGG architecture and has four times less weights than DeepSpectra, while it gave comparable classification results and performed more stable across different pre-training routines. This is expected, since the establishment of an efficient neural network architecture for spectral data requires to cope with a high co-linearity which in combination with fully-connected layers increases dramatically the number of weights in neural networks. While in SpectraVGG we used pooling layers to address the problem of high co-linearity, it is worth noting that pooling may obscure peak shifts. Position of peaks can shift due to chemical changes, and therefore the peak shifts may contain important

information. Through pooling operations we may lose this information and therefore pooling may represent a suboptimal solution for a high co-linearity problem.

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